

Interaction of Oxovanadium(IV) with Some Amino Acids[†]

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Manuscript received 20 February 1984, revised 30 July 1984, accepted 19 January 1985

The equilibria between VO(IV) ions and some L amino acids, like L-cysteine, L histidine and L-phenylalanine in aqueous solution for the pH range 2-11 at 25, 35 and 45° and at an ionic strength of 0.15 M KNO₃ have been studied. Besides investigating the complex equilibria, the thermodynamic parameters, i.e. ΔG, ΔH and ΔS have also been evaluated.

THE importance of metal ions in biological system led many bioinorganic chemist to investigate equilibria between metal ions and biological ligands in aqueous solution. The vanadium ion has been thought to be an essential element in both animals and plants¹. The mechanism of transport of metal ions is poorly understood. Any progress in this area requires equilibrium studies. The VO(IV)-amino acids system has been of interest to many workers in the field of metal complexation. The stability constants for VO(IV) complexes with DL-methionine, L-threonine, L-phenylalanine have been reported by Sekhon and Chopra². Complex of oxovanadium with cysteine methylester have been studied by Sakuri and coworkers³ and suggested the stoichiometry 2 : 1 (ligand : metal). We, therefore, carried out systematic potentiometric studies to determine the stability constants and in addition, we have also determined the thermodynamic parameters for VO(IV)-L-amino acids system.

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical grade. Potentiometric titrations were carried out on a series of solution, 0.02 M HNO₃ containing combination of 1.0 × 10⁻³ M cation (as sulphate) and 4.0 × 10⁻³ M anion of L-cysteine, L-histidine and L-phenylalanine under constant ionic strength (0.15 M KNO₃). Titration were carried out at 25, 35 and 45° maintained by immersing the experimental vessel in a thermostat (U-10) having a control accuracy ±0.02°. The pK_a values of some anions under similar condition were also determined. Two different methods were used to treat the experimental data, (i) interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values and (ii) interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values.

The nature of the overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been calculated at three different temperatures and at fixed ionic strength 0.15 M (KNO₃) with the help of temperature coefficient and Gibb's-Helmoltz equation.

Results and Discussion

Calculated complex formation constants for both hydrogen ions and VO(IV) complexes, are given in Table 1. The hydrogen ion complex formation constants reported in Table 1 are in good agreement with the literature values. The values of ΔG, ΔH and ΔS calculated at three different temperature are reported in Table 2. Assuming that a major part at the error in log K are systematic, the precision for ΔG value is 1.0 kcal mole⁻¹, for ΔH is ±1.0 kcal mol⁻¹ and for ΔS is ±2.0 cal deg⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

It is observed from the stability constants and thermodynamic data that complex formed with L-cysteine is more stable than L-phenylalanine and L-histidine. This may be due to the decrease in basicity of the ligands. It can also be assumed from the values of the stability constants of the L-cysteine complex that the ligand acts as tridentate giving rise to two stepwise complexes. Whereas in the L-phenylalanine and L-histidine the ligands act as bidentate giving rise to one step complexes. This is also apparent from the thermodynamic data

TABLE 1—COMPLEX FORMATION CONSTANTS OF L-CYSTEINE, L-HISTIDINE AND L-PHENYLALANINE WITH VO(IV) AT $\mu=0.15$ M (KNO₃)

System	Dissociation constant	25°		35°		45°	
		A	B	A	B	A	B
L-Cysteine	log K ₁ ^H	8.20	8.20	8.10	8.12	7.98	7.99
L-Histidine	log K ₁ ^H	8.80	8.82	8.78	8.81	8.70	8.76
	log K ₂ ^H	5.80	5.83	5.75	5.79	5.70	5.76
L-Phenylalanine	log K ₁ ^H	9.02	9.03	8.98	8.99	8.95	8.98
	Formation constant						
VO(IV)-Cysteine	log K ₁	5.78	5.80	6.01	6.03	6.27	6.32
	log K ₂	3.19	3.10	3.89	3.85	5.06	5.02
VO(IV)-Histidine	log K ₁	9.79	9.80	9.28	9.30	9.04	9.05
VO(IV)-Phenylalanine	log K ₁	7.58	7.60	7.24	7.25	6.73	6.75

† Presented in the Convention of Chemists, Outback, 1983.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT $\mu = 0.15 M$

System	Temp °C	ΔG kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
VO(IV)-Cysteine	25	-9.858		
	35	-9.682	+11.09	+57.42
	45	-9.838		
VO(IV)-Histidine	25	-13.364		
	35	-13.108	-15.538	-8.09
	45	-13.169		
VO(IV)-Phenyl- alanine	25	-18.36		
	35	-10.22	-24.37	-46.08
	45	-9.97		

available, that the entropy change is more +ve for the L-cysteine complex than the corresponding complexes of L-phenylalanine and L-histidine. The presence of SH group in L-cysteine results in increasing the basicity of the ligand and hence more stability of the complex. The ΔH value for the VO(IV)-L-cysteine complex indicates that the formation of complex is endothermic (+ ΔH). In spite of this unfavourable enthalpy change, the complex is stabilised by relatively large +ve entropy

change. This result is found analogous to those reported⁴⁻⁶ for metal carboxylate complexes. The negative value of enthalpy indicates that the formation of these complexes are exothermic ($-\Delta H$). However, lower stability of these complexes can be explained due to high negative value of entropy.

Acknowledgement

Authors are grateful to Prof. K. N. Munshi, Head, Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University for facilities.

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